

Good practices to strengthen the evaluation of the future impact of the CAP Strategic Plans

OBJECTIVES AND CHALLENGES

Member States have conducted several **ex-ante analyses** for the preparation of the CAP Strategic Plans, as required by Reg. 2115/2021 (Art. 107). The evaluation of the future impact of the strategic plans can be challenging for several reasons. It should be conducted within a relatively limited period of time, often when the final strategic plans are not yet available, whereas several different interventions and objectives need to be accounted for. Bringing together the results of different evaluations can be difficult, while **certain analyses would require the use of complex and time-demanding tools**. Also, it is not always clear how ex-ante analyses and stakeholder consultations should inform one another.

GOOD PRACTICES

Promoting early evaluation

The introduction of new interventions, such as eco-schemes, highlights the **need to define evaluation plans** early on in the process. Doing so will significantly contribute to a more robust ex-ante evaluation. This would be particularly **relevant for the next programming period**. The promotion of early evaluation is also considered effective when a multiphase approach to evaluation is adopted. While this **allows evaluators to provide feedback during each stage of the CSP drafting**, it must also be considered in relation to the fact that it may hinder a wider holistic view of the CSP.

Evaluate the final approved CSP

Approximately two-thirds of the ex-ante evaluations were carried out based on a draft CSP, often on specific chapters, which hinders the holistic view. As a result, the **evaluation of coherence**, notably external coherence, proved to be **challenging** for the evaluators. Without minimising the first recommendation to promote early evaluation, ex-ante evaluation report should be **revised in light of the approved CSP and in its entirety**. This, in turn, will allow the ex-ante evaluation process to improve the quality of the design of the CSP and to establish clearly the potential contribution of the CSPs at the national and EU levels.

Leverage lessons learned from past programming periods

While lessons learned were acknowledged, their importance lies not in recognising them but in **understanding how they contribute to the design of the CSPs**. This is especially important for ensuring better adoption by farmers, pinpointing necessary improvements and achieving **more efficient implementation**.

Promote the use of visual tools

The use of visual tools has proven to be very helpful throughout the various stages of the ex-ante evaluations. In several instances, visual tools were used to **gain a better understanding** of how interventions respond to the identified needs, how they are possibly linked to each other and/or to result indicators, and how they potentially contribute to the CAP specific objectives. These tools can **enhance the clarity and accessibility of complex information**, improving the communication of findings and recommendations.

Targeted strategic stakeholder engagement

Stakeholder involvement should be used strategically to ensure meaningful engagement and **prevent potential stakeholder fatigue** between the various consultation processes carried out during the drafting of the strategic plans. Under the scope of the ex-ante evaluation, a **targeted consultative process** that effectively captures diverse perspectives and expertise, and that can inform and **be informed by the evaluation at clear stages**, would be recommended.

Find more insights in the Inventory of tools online